

CDE4Peace

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CONCEPT DEVELOPMENT AND EXPERIMENTATION FOR EU CONFLICT PREVENTION AND PEACE-BUILDING (CDE4PEACE)

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Working paper on strategic concepts

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Executive Summary

This Working paper presents a review of several prominent strategic concepts and approaches in the area of EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding. The desk review has been carried out under WP3 (Review) of the CDE4Peace project. The review is focussed on resilience and the integrated approach; ‘conflict sensitivity’ and ‘the whole-of-society’ concept. The Working paper seeks to extract the main features of strategic concepts in EU peacebuilding for a potential application in quantitative research. A method for decomposing strategic concepts into quantifiable variables by means of peace indicators is elaborated.

1. Introduction

Strategic-level concepts in EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding contain political assessments, objectives and guidance. These are typically outlined in strategic policy documents or legal acts such as the European Security Strategy, the EU Global Strategy or the Lisbon Treaty. Characteristic examples of strategic concepts in EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding are resilience and the integrated approach¹; the comprehensive approach², crisis management, stabilisation, the liberal peace concept³ and post-liberal peace⁴. Some of the concepts such as liberal peace, resilience, sovereignty or common strategic culture could be considered metapolitical in nature as they are subjects of theoretical or philosophical political science. In some of these cases, most notably with regard to resilience and liberal peace the term ‘paradigm’ is equally justified.

The concept-scoping in this Working paper employs qualitative research methods from conflict and peace studies. As a first step desk review of selected strategic concepts in EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding is conducted. A critical-constructive approach is applied in order to explore and analyse the maturity level of the selected concepts. The concept-scoping gives answer to the research question: What are the features of strategic concepts in EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding? After extracting the main concept features, the Working paper explores the possibility for converting some structural components of the strategic concepts into quantifiable variables – a process which could have applied research applications. The quantification method could provide an important (and missing) methodological link between the qualitative research methods from conflict and peace studies and quantitative, experimentation tools (including software tools for concept development & experimentation).

The Working paper is focussed on three prominent strategic concepts in the field of EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding: resilience and the integrated approach (as set out in the EU Global Strategy); ‘conflict sensitivity’ (elaborated under the EUNPACK research project⁵) and the ‘whole-of-society’ concept (developed under the WOSCAP research project⁶). The selected strategic concepts have diverse backgrounds. Resilience and the integrated approach represent mainstream EU concepts, whereas ‘conflict sensitivity’ and the ‘whole-of-society’ concept are research-based and academically-brewed concepts. They provide insights into the deep currents that run below strategic thinking on contemporary EU peacebuilding. Last but not least, the selected strategic concepts showcase the prevalent structure and characteristic features of these specific intellectual and social constructs.

¹ European Union Global Strategy, Shared Vision, Common Action: A Stronger Europe. A Global Strategy for the European Union’s Foreign and Security Policy (Brussels 2016): 28-29.

² European Commission and HR/VP, Joint Communication to the European Parliament and the Council: The EU’s Comprehensive Approach to External Conflicts and Crises (Brussels: European Commission, 11.12.2013). On the comprehensive approach, see for example: Nicoletta Pirozzi, *The EU’s Comprehensive Approach to Crisis Management* (DCAF Brussels – EU Crisis Management Papers Series 2013).

³ On the democratic / liberal peace concept, see: Bruce M. Russett, *Grasping the Democratic Peace: Principles for a Post-Cold War World* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1993); Michael W. Doyle, ‘Three Pillars of the Liberal Peace’, *The American Political Science Review* 99, no.3 (2005): 463-466.

⁴ The first radical critique of the liberal peace concept is: Oliver Richmond, *The Transformation of Peace* (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2005). The critique is further developed in: Oliver Richmond, *A Post-Liberal Peace* (London: Routledge, 2011).

⁵ EUNPACK – A conflict-sensitive unpacking of the EU comprehensive approach to conflict and crisis mechanisms, website: <http://www.eunpack.eu>

⁶ WOSCAP – Whole-of-society conflict prevention and peacebuilding, website: <http://www.woscap.eu>

2. Resilience and the integrated approach

Resilience and the integrated approach have been elaborated as closely interlinked concept and approach in the EU Global Strategy (EUGS).⁷ Both resilience and the integrated approach are listed among the five key strategic priorities of EU External Action.⁸ However, they are contextualized in a different manner. Resilience is defined as a broader concept, encompassing all individuals and the whole of society. The ideal of a resilient state and resilient society is proclaimed. The EU declares its will to promote the resilience of states and societies to the east stretching to Central Asia, and south down to Central Africa. However, the geopolitical and defence implications of the resilience concept are not sufficiently discussed in the document. The EU Global Strategy provides an academically credible definition of resilience – the ability of states and societies to reform, thus withstanding and recovering from internal and external crises. The concept of resilience has been interpreted by Juncos as the new EU foreign policy paradigm.⁹ Examining the rise of resilience discourses in EU foreign policy she argues that the discourse of resilience in the EUGS chimes well with a pragmatist turn in social sciences and global governance. While the actuality of a pragmatist turn in the social sciences might be contested, the rise of the resilience concept in many policy areas is real. Resilience has been interpreted even broader in terms of ideology in the context of international statebuilding.¹⁰ In practical terms the rise of the resilience concept has given birth to an academic journal with the same name. In this context resilience could be characterised as a ‘concept-journal’.

The integrated approach, or more broadly integration is defined in the EUGS as a multi-dimensional, multi-phased, multi-level and multi-lateral approach through the use of all available policies and instruments aimed at conflict prevention, management and resolution. Multilateralism as part of the integrated approach is a good example of a concept within a concept. Defining concepts by means of other concepts is one of the tricky methods in the concept development business.

As noted by Tardy, the concept of an integrated approach to conflicts and crises in the EUGS can be interpreted in two different ways.¹¹ First the integrated approach can be seen as a more ambitious, more political and longer-term approach to conflict response, whereas the comprehensive approach was presented as first and foremost a general working method, i.e. also more politically neutral. The integrated approach is more strategic in the sense that it goes beyond the operational aspects of crisis response to better integrate the political, economic and security dimensions of the EU’s response. The other way to interpret the integrated approach is to see it as being more operational, i.e. as a means to operationalise the comprehensive approach. Overall, the integrated approach is always seen in a comparative perspective with the comprehensive approach. In practical terms, the launch of the integrated approach has brought about the establishment of a specific administrative unit within the EEAS in 2017, the PRISM unit which was replaced in 2019 with a whole directorate ‘Integrated Approach for Security and Peace’ (ISP). In this context the concept of an integrated approach could be characterised as a ‘concept-directorate’.

⁷ For an account of the inside story of this collective document, see: Nathalie Tocci, *Framing the EU Global Strategy* (London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2017).

⁸ European Union Global Strategy, 23-32.

⁹ Ana E. Juncos, ‘Resilience as the New EU Foreign Policy Paradigm: A Pragmatist Turn?’, *European Security* 26, no.1 (2017): 1-7.

¹⁰ David Chandler, ‘International Statebuilding and the Ideology of Resilience’, *Politics* 33, no.4 (2013): 276-286.

¹¹ Thierry Tardy, ‘The EU: from Comprehensive Vision to Integrated Action’, *European Union Institute for Security Studies Brief Issue* (Feb.2017).

3. Conflict sensitivity

Conflict sensitivity is one of the rising stars in the universe of EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding. The concept, which originates from development and humanitarian assistance discourses has been further elaborated under the EU Horizon 2020 research project EUNPACK (A conflict-sensitive unpacking of the EU comprehensive approach to conflict and crisis mechanisms). In the spirit of the current turn to the 'local' in academic literature the project has provided new insights into how EU crisis response functions and how it is being received and perceived by local beneficiaries.¹² One of the project's main conclusions is that it is difficult to find any evidence of conflict sensitivity being operationalised and mainstreamed by the EU in all three geographical areas where the Union has been engaged in conflict prevention and peacebuilding (the enlargement area, the neighbourhood area and the extended neighbourhood area).¹³ This is seen as a clear example of the implementation-perception gap in EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding. In an attempt to fill this gap the EUNPACK project elaborates conflict sensitivity as a novel concept able to overcome the shortcomings of current EU policies.¹⁴ Conflict sensitivity is defined as the ability of an organisation to understand the context in which it operates, to understand the interaction between its intervention and the context; and to act upon the understanding of this interaction, in order to minimise negative impacts and maximise positive impacts.¹⁵ One of the main policy recommendations is that the EU needs a conflict sensitive approach in order to break the crisis cycle and produce sustainable peace. Conflict sensitivity in the context of EU crisis response would imply recognizing the complexity and the multiple layers of conflict as well as that different groups in a conflict have different perceptions on root causes of conflict and legitimate actions and agents. Conflict sensitivity and local ownership are considered as interlinked concepts.

One of the practical shortcomings of 'conflict sensitivity' is that the 'romantic charm of the local' might not be appealing to many of those working in the competent EU institutions, missions and operations. It is not fully clear how conflict-sensitivity could be interpreted by policy-makers and to what extent it would be implemented on the ground. The willingness of the EU staff to apply a conflict-sensitive approach to a variety of local groups and marginalised communities cannot be taken for granted. Moreover, conflict sensitivity has certain ambiguities. It is embedded in an over-theorised framework of four generations of peacebuilding¹⁶, a framework which does not fit the humble empirical reality of

¹² Morten Bøås and Pernille Rieker, *EUNPACK Executive Summary of the Final Report and Selected Policy Recommendations* (Brussels: Centre for European Policy Studies, March 2019): 5.

¹³ *Ibid.*, 12.

¹⁴ Pernille Rieker and Steven Blockmans, 'Plugging the Capability-Expectations Gap: towards Effective, Comprehensive and Conflict-sensitive EU Crisis Response', *European Security* 28, no.1 (2019): 1-21.

¹⁵ Conflict-Sensitive Approaches to Development, Humanitarian Assistance and Peacebuilding', London: Resource Pack (International Alert and Saferworld, 2004): 1.

¹⁶ On the four generations of peacebuilding, see Oliver Richmond, *Maintaining Order, Making Peace* (Basingstoke: Palgrave, 2002); and Oliver Richmond, 'Eirenisism and a Post-liberal Peace', *Review of International Studies* 35, no.3 (2009): 557-580.

EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding. Actually, conflict sensitivity could be characterised as a ‘luxury concept’ in the ‘valley of tears’.¹⁷

4. ‘Whole-of-society’ concept

Similar to conflict sensitivity, the whole-of-society concept has been developed under an EU Horizon 2020 research project, WOSCAP (Whole-of-Society Conflict Prevention and Peacebuilding). The whole-of-society concept is developed in comparative perspective and opposed to the traditional ‘whole-of-government’ approach.¹⁸ This is a typical case of dialectical concept development when a concept is derived as opposed to a previous concept, which is often perceived as a failed one. While whole-of-government approaches primarily focus on the need for internal coordination and integration between various policy domains (especially development, diplomacy and defence) and tools of intervention, the whole-of-society approach adds an additional layer of inclusive engagement by emphasising the roles of, and relations with, a wide range of social actors in the countries of intervention.¹⁹ It pays particular attention to the need to engage various constituencies beyond the state – such as local community leaders, traditional authorities, minority groups, the private sector, religious organisations, women and youth – who have often been excluded or marginalised by the state. The underlying assumption of the ‘whole-of-society’ concept is that by extending the range of actors with a stake in peacebuilding beyond what most external actors usually practice, and by recasting the nature and focus of their engagement and interaction, intervention is more likely to facilitate processes conducive to stable and sustainable peace.²⁰ A ‘whole-of-society’ approach deals explicitly with issues of poor coordination and integration, aims to counter fragmentation within the policy process, promote synergies and make better collective use of resources. The prescriptive and normative ideal of the ‘whole-of-society’ concept emphasises the importance of inclusivity and local ownership.

The ‘whole-of-society’ concept has the ambition to provide an intellectual breakthrough in the assessment of the EU’s civilian conflict prevention and peacebuilding capabilities. The limitations of the ‘whole-of-society’ concept can be found in its normative assumptions, minimizing the role of the nation-states (EU Member States) and national defence capabilities. Secondly, the ‘whole-of-society’ concept out of necessity presupposes a certain institutional totality which does not match the current fragmentation of EU sovereignty in conflict prevention and peacebuilding. In this train of thought, the ‘whole-of-society’ concept has some of the deficiencies of the mainstream comprehensive approach. It is a ‘concept-prescription’.

¹⁷ In an interview in May 2019, before being appointed HR/VP and Head of the EEAS Josep Borrell described the EU Foreign Affairs Council as “more a valley of tears than a centre of decision-making” because “it’s where all the open sores of humanity come. They tell us their sufferings, we express our condolences and concern ... but no capacity for action comes out of it and we just move on to the next one.” The interview is available at: https://www.ecfr.eu/article/commentary_borrell_returns_his_vision_for_europe

¹⁸ Mary Martin, Vesna Bozicic-Dzelilovic and Linda Benrais, ‘Mind the Gaps. A Whole-of-Society Approach to Peacebuilding and Conflict Prevention’, *Peacebuilding* 6, no.1 (2018): 171-182.

¹⁹ Karin Göldner-Ebenthal and Véronique Dudouet, *From Power Mediation to Dialogue Support: Assessing the European Union’s Capabilities for Multi-track Diplomacy* (Berlin: Berghof Foundation research report, 2017), 8-9.

²⁰ Mary Martin, Vesna Bozicic-Dzelilovic, Chris van der Borgh and Georg Frerks, *WOSCAP D2.9 Theoretical and Methodological Framework*, (London: London School of Economics and Utrecht University, May 2016), 6.

As a result of the concept-scoping the main features of strategic concepts could be extracted, as shown on table 1.

Concept	Novelty	Public appeal	Ideal	Missing elements	Definition	Policies	Links with other concepts
Resilience	Not present in the previous EU strategic document (European Security Strategy)	Formally wide public consultations of the EUGS were held. The real public appeal remains unclear.	Resilient state and society	Geopolitical and defence implications of resilience	Credible in academic terms	Enlargement policy; European Neighbourhood Policy; Migration policy	Integrated approach; Whole-of-society concept
Integrated approach	Further development of the comprehensive approach, similar to the UN's broad concept of integration	Way more technocratic for the wider European public	Increased cohesion of the EU's crisis response	No clear centre of gravity in institutional terms	Credible in academic terms, but multiple interpretations are possible	Pre-emptive peace; security and stabilisation; conflict settlement; political economy of peace	Resilience, comprehensive approach; human security
Conflict sensitivity	Comparative novelty for EU institutions	The need to communicate clearly with a broad spectrum of the population is emphasized.	Making the EU's crisis response mechanisms more conflict and context sensitive	Perceptions of the EU staff in peacebuilding missions / operations	Credible in academic terms, with some ambiguities.	Developmental state-building; Administrative capacity-building	Local ownership
Whole-of-society	Derived from a human security approach; the term is present in the EUGS	Inclusivity of social groups (including marginalised) is emphasized.	Sustainable and inclusive peacebuilding	The role of nation-states is minimized; The concept's assumption that the EU is able to act in an institutional totality is presently not realistic.	Credible in academic terms.	Multi-track diplomacy; governance reform and security sector reform	Whole-of-government approach; Human security; Local ownership

Table 1. Strategic concepts' features

The review and decomposition of strategic concepts in the area of EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding shows several common features and structural components. The concept is a term or a phrase with a high level of abstraction. The precise meaning (or semantics) of the term is shaped in the complex EU policy process by policy-makers, civil society organizations and researchers who more often than not have different interests and interpretations of the term. As noted in a research report, the multiple usage of the same term presents a serious policy challenge that should be addressed by

way of greater conceptual clarity – ensuring that all actors attach the same meaning to these terms.²¹ As a rule the definitions of concepts are academically credible, yet unstable and volatile when it comes to practical implementation. It is difficult to give a concrete example for the practical implementation of any of the strategic EU peacebuilding concepts under review. Concepts are generally perceived as social constructs which tend to be averse to practical implementation. In some respects, they look delicate and otherworldly. Therefore, definitions' analysis and semantics do not offer great prospects for unpacking and explaining strategic concepts.

A key feature of any strategic concept is the claim for novelty. This is achieved on first place by coining a new term (phrase) or borrowing one from another international actor as was the case with the comprehensive approach, which was borrowed from NATO. Secondly, novelty is attained by opposing the new concept to an old one. This dialectical model of concept generation is constantly repeated. The concept's ideal is usually dressed in political correctness and flowery phraseology which is acceptable across the broader European political spectrum. The downside of these 'concepts-ideals' is that they are regarded as just another political talk ('EU speak') and do not have a wide appeal across Europe. In fact, the perceptions of European societies towards different EU peace concepts have not been sufficiently studied. Therefore, popular support for this EU policy area to large extent remains a mystery.

The complex links between the concepts under review show that they belong to the same 'concept constellation'. All four concepts are theoretically embedded in critical constructivism as one of the major schools of thought in international relations.²² Indeed, this postpositivist theory has strong positions in the mainstream political discourse and scholarship on EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding. Other schools of thought (e.g. Realism) are not adequately developed at the European level. Moreover, all four concepts originate from Western Europe, while Eastern Europe is underrepresented in the concept development process with only few individual researchers or experts involved in one way or another.

Another common feature of all strategic concepts are one or more missing elements which can be analytically traced. The missing element is often the result of methodological reductionism, whereas the explanatory and constructive potential of the concept is reduced. In many cases the development of a fair concept of EU peacebuilding comes with a price, the price of reduction and simplification of the complex reality of conflicts. This is connected both with generalizations and normative assumptions and is one of the main reasons for the practical difficulties when it comes to implementing strategic concepts on the ground.

²¹ Ana Juncos et al., *EU-CIVCAP D1.2 Executive Summary of Final Report including Guidance for Policymakers* (Bristol: University of Bristol, 2018), 10.

²² On constructivism in international relations, see: Alexander Wendt, *Social Theory of International Politics* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1999).

5. Quantification of strategic concepts and its limitations

The concept-scoping shows that policies are the incarnation of strategic concepts. Policies are one of the few components of strategic concepts which potentially could be subject to quantification. This holds true especially for specific policies implemented in a concrete conflict-stricken country, given that the policy is clearly defined and reliable data gathering and processing is practically achievable. Very importantly, the policy should be generated under the framework of a strategic concept. When these preconditions are met, policies could be converted into concrete programmes and projects. Programmes and projects could be measured and evaluated in an unbiased way by means of peace indicators which are quantifiable variables. The proposed CDE4Peace method for decomposing strategic concepts into quantifiable variables is shown on fig.1.

Figure 1: Method for decomposing strategic concepts into quantifiable variables

The quantification of EU peacebuilding concepts is very useful in practical terms as quantifiable variables are meaningful to software tools, including tools for concept development and experimentation (CDE). The added value of quantification is in that it enhances the scientific credibility of future research in this area and makes possible an important (and missing) methodological link between qualitative research methods from conflict and peace studies and quantitative methods and tools. As noted in the Guidance of the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), evaluations of peacebuilding and conflict prevention activities tend to be weak in terms of data, methods and validity of findings.²³ The proposed CDE4Peace method is a conscious attempt to help overcome those weaknesses, specifically with regard to EU peacebuilding concepts and policies. The proposed quantification method draws on methods from quantitative assessment of resilience of complex systems, such as critical infrastructures.²⁴

Peace indicators play a crucial role in the CDE4Peace quantification method of EU strategic concepts and policies in the area of EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding. Peace indicators could be regarded as key performance indicators (KPIs) for EU peacebuilding concepts and policies. Key performance indicators are traditionally used for evaluating and measuring the impact from

²³ Evaluating Peacebuilding Activities in Settings of Conflict and Fragility, OECD 2012: 7

²⁴ David Angeler and Craig Allen, 'Quantifying Resilience' *Journal of Applied Ecology* Vol.53, (2016): 617-624.; Alexander Jovanovic, Knut Oien and Amrita Choudhary, 'An indicator-based approach to assessing resilience of smart critical infrastructures' – In: *Urban Disaster Resilience and Security. Addressing Risks in Societies*, 2018: 285-311; Nikolay Pavlov and Stefan Hadjitodorov, *Quantifying Resilience: A Case Study on Critical Infrastructure Resilience in the Republic of Bulgaria*. In: *Proceedings of the NATO Crisis Management and Disaster Response Centre of Excellence (CMDR COE)*, 2019: 77-92.

programmes and projects. Peace indicators could be used specifically for measuring the effect of programmes and projects developed under EU strategic concepts and policies. Peace indicators entail three main components, as follows:

- 1) Expert assessments;
- 2) Public perception surveys; and
- 3) Peace data.

The integration of the three components lends scientific reliability to the proposed quantification method for EU policies developed under a certain strategic concept. Expert assessments are a traditional approach for informed and knowledge-based evaluation of complex systems. Some of the key requirements in the assessment process are the choice of independent experts, high level of competence and lack of conflict of interests. Public perception surveys must display quantitatively the perceptions of local populations towards EU policies on the ground. Of course, local perceptions might differ from expert assessments in some respects. Peace data is the third key element of peace indicators. Peace data should include data on:

- number of victims from a conflict for a given period after a peacebuilding policy / programme / project has been launched;
- number of affected persons and casualties for a given period after a peacebuilding policy / programme / project has been launched;
- disruptions of critical infrastructures as a result of a conflict (before and after the start of a peacebuilding policy / programme / project);
- number of trained personnel under a peacebuilding programme / project;
- communications between the conflicting parties facilitated by a peace programme / project;
- number of renovated homes and critical infrastructures under a peacebuilding programme / project;

Aggregating the results from expert assessments, public perception surveys and peace data allows for calculating the peace indicators of a given strategic concepts. The process could be reiterated for greater precision of the results. The peace indicators could be compared with the indicators of alternative concepts. This process, however is not straightforward and one should be aware of the possible limitations. Overall, quantitative methods in the social sciences have focussed primarily on survey research and analysis with statistical methods.²⁵ Similarly the analysis of quantitative data in peace research has also been done by use of formal statistical methods. The CDE4Peace project takes into account the limitations of quantitative work as specified by Ron Smith who argues that quantitative peace research could be improved if authors put more emphasis on the substantive issues and less on the mechanical application of rule-based, statistical techniques.²⁶

In this context, a meaningful application of the proposed quantification method would be possible only if certain conditions are met. High-quality peace data relatable to the respective strategic concept is needed. None of the three strategic concepts which have been explored could presently be converted into reliable peace data. This is connected both with the high level of abstraction of strategic concepts

²⁵ Daniel Stockemer, *Quantitative methods for the social sciences*, Springer 2019.

²⁶ Ron P. Smith, 'Quantitative Methods in Peace Research', *Journal of Peace Research* vol.35, no.4 (1998): 419-427.

and the complexity of peace research data in general. The quality of the data about policies developed under an EU strategic concept is crucial. It is only by high-quality peace data that measurable policy variables could be defined, hence peace concepts could be measured and “proven true or false”. And last but not least, a quantification method could be employed only if the concepts are fully developed and they can be converted into policies, programmes and projects. Half-concepts do not constitute a valid research subject for quantitative research.

6. Conclusion

The review of concepts in this Working paper focussed on three prominent strategic concepts and approaches in the area of EU conflict prevention and peacebuilding: resilience and the integrated approach; ‘conflict sensitivity’ and ‘the whole-of-society’ concept. The review and decomposition of strategic concepts show several common features and structural components: a claim for novelty; ideal state and academically credible definition; public appeal; missing elements; links with other concepts and policies. Namely policies are the incarnation of strategic concepts. Policies are one of the few components of strategic concepts which potentially could be subject to quantification. Policies could be converted into programmes and projects which in turn could be measured and evaluated in an unbiased way by means of peace indicators which are quantifiable variables. On this basis a method for decomposing strategic concepts into quantifiable variables is elaborated which converts strategic concepts into peace indicators. Peace indicators entail three main components: expert assessments; public perception surveys; and peace data. The meaningful application of the proposed quantification method would be possible only if high-quality peace data is available and the strategic concept is fully developed.